

Organizational Culture and Hotel-Quality Services Delivery in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu; Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: Organizational culture is the collection of business practices, ethics, processes, and interactions that make up the work environment more favorable and productive. Due to the pivotal role organizational culture plays in the hotel business, managers and hotel owners invest heavily in human and material resources to bridge the communication gap. However, there are still inconsistencies and lacuna between the employer and employees in the hotel industry in Enugu Metropolis which do result in a hostile and unpleasant working environment leading to poor service delivery. This study examined the relationship that exists between organizational culture and hotels quality service delivery in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design and data were collected from respondents with the aid of a structured questionnaire. Collected data were analyzed using the arithmetic mean. Hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment correlation Coefficient via Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS 23). Findings showed that there is a significant relationship between organizational behavior and quality service delivery in hotels in Enugu Metropolis. The study concluded that organizational culture has a great impact on the quality of services hotels in Enugu Metropolis offers to the customer, and recommended that management of hotels in Enugu Metropolis should inculcate the organizational value and international best practices to the functionality of her staff as that will help sell out the organizational image to the satisfaction of their customers which is ultimate in the hotel business.

KEYWORDS: Enugu, Hotels, Organization-Culture, and Quality Service Delivery.

INTRODUCTION

As a result of global businesses, organizations now grow to contend not only with their local cultures, but the global one and hotels in Enugu metropolis are not only adapting to the innovative technologies, best global cultures, and practices but are also proactive in responding to the trends as they unfold, act smartly and internally to remain in the competitive business environment. An organization can be referred to as an organized group of people with peculiar characteristics, purpose, ideas, and ideology to achieve a common goal while culture is the ideas, beliefs, customs, and behavioral patterns of a given people in the society.

Organizational culture therefore can be referred to as the mode of procedure, operations, behavioral pattern, and values that binds organizational members together for the organizational aims and objectives. It is worthy of note that while some organizations develop and build their cultural heritage to guide and shape their organizational activities, others tend to import, refine and adapt the cultural languages, behaviors, attitudes, and even cultural changes in the external environment depending on the nature of business and or organization. Organizational culture stems to have its root from the societal norms and values from where they operate (Anoke, 2020). It is a proper way to behave within the organization that entails shared beliefs, systematic values recognized by the authorities and leaders then communicate and strengthened through various means aimed at shaping employee mindset, behaviors, and understanding for the organizational aims and objectives.

Orogbu and Onyeizugbe (2015) noted that a business organization should build and grow her culture from the society from which she operates to ensure organizational sustainability and survival. In other words, an organization is made up of individuals, groups, and members with different identities, ideologies, vision and mission fused for the betterment of the organizational goals and objective(Osita,) Onu(2019) noted that sometimes, cultural background, parental upbringing and societal value seems to conflict in terms of goals, values, lifestyle and behavior set out for the organization and these no doubt do affect the organization if not well managed timely by the concern authorities. Kings and Lui (2018) argued that organizational output to large extent is predicated on the quality of the cultural practices exhibited in the said organization.

According to Eze (2018), the product quality, content, services rendered, and product value in any given organization represents the culture of an organization. When high-quality services are embedded in a business organizational vision and mission statement that directs and guides the overall operation of the firm, the employees strive to offer high-quality services and products by establishing a high standard and maintaining operational ethics which are required to remain in a competitive business environment.

Organizational Culture and Hotel-Quality Services Delivery in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu; Nigeria

Enugu Metropolis, in Enugu State Nigeria, is known for her quality hotel services because the city is not only the commercial nerve center of the Eastern part of Nigeria with five states but it is also regarded as the political capital of the region with a lot of commercial and political activities therein daily. These hotels are operating in a competitive and saturated environment and survival by the fittest becomes the order of the day. Okpanel(2017) noted that to navigate through these trouble business waters, the culture of the organization, as well as the types and quality of services rendered, play a pivotal role in achieving the desired outcomes.

Competitive advantage among the hotels in this part of the world seems to be based on managerial approach, organizational standard, operating procedure, and quality services rendered to customers who are the ultimate deciding factor. Customers' patronage and retention in a hotel depend largely on the services he/she got from that particular hotel. While some customers may stick to a particular hotel due to the mode of operation like quick food service, laundry uniqueness service, and timely delivery, others opted for a saline environment, adequate security especially with the insecurity at its peak in Nigeria today, and fair pricing.

Richond (2019) noted that organizational value seems to vary from an organization, region, society, or even country. Hotels, for instance, use different strategies to edge their competitors. Such strategies are but are not limited to place value on customer relation, content value in the meal, prompt room service, and service value such as employee dress code. In all, the need to offer quality services remains the focus of most managers in the hotel business in the Enugu metropolis while total quality management embedded in organizational culture is continually neglected.

Rich (2015) opined that total quality management is arguably the most remarkable way towards improving quality services in any organization. This no doubt entails the organizational long term planning, concerted and continues commitment by all parties towards improving quality, excellence, value products and services to meet and possibly exceed customers' expectations and satisfaction who are the ultimate deciding factor in the business through active involvement and participation of all members at all levels and upholding firm's ethics and code of conduct. This will certainly lead to quality and excellent service delivery and of great impact on productivity.

In the opinion of Warzecha(2017), organizational behavior deals with how people within the components that make up the entity interact and network to achieve organizational goals and objectives. He argued that a hotel may want to have the best service delivery as her vision but with poor, unvisionary, and unethical behavior of employees who may not want to key into the dream of the management can thwart the whole process through poor cultural practices. This will certainly, affect the patronage level and customer retention level of the firm.

Despite the attention being paid to the organizational culture by management and owners of hotels in Enugu Metropolis due to the pivotal roles it plays in the industry, there is still inconsistency and communication gap between the employer and employees in the hotel industry in Enugu Metropolis which do result to a hostile and unpleasant working environment and poor service delivery. It is against this backdrop that the researcher deemed it fit to investigate the relationship between organizational culture and hotel-quality service delivery in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State.

As a result of the strategic position of Enugu Metropolis in the economic and political map of not only the south Eastern states of Nigeria but Nigeria at large, the choice of Enugu Metropolis as the research domain of this study is a point in the right direction.

In line with the objective of the study, the following hypothesis was postulated and tested:

Ho1: Organizational Culture has no significant effect on hotel quality service delivery in Enugu Metropolis.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Concept of Organizational Culture

The values of an organization to a great extent affects the productivity of the organization as it shapes and remolds the ways people behave, factoring all contingency issues when drawing plans, programs, and procedures geared towards developing organizational rules, conduct, ethics, and practices that will guide and protect the organization as well as the rights and privileges of the employees while achieving the organizational goals through quality services.

While value guide planning, decision-making, control mechanism and sense of what is important, what should be done, and how it should be done in the right and proper way in an organization; the culture of the organization is the collection of business practices, ethics, processes and interactions that make up the work environment more favorable and productive.

Kubaisi(2012) argued that organizational culture is a set of agreed meanings set out to govern the conduct of individual components that make up the unit. These include but are not limited to principles, standards, values, ethics, attitudes, emotions, actions, and inactions that control and direct the conduct of its members. Organizational culture can also be referred to as the concept of joint arrangement of the mindset towards achieving the organizational goals. It equally helps to unite the individual idea which is distinct from the members of other groups. Therefore, organizational culture comprises the personal opinion, beliefs, morals, values, ethics, habits, and practices shared by one group or members of a specific community, as culture is believed to differ from one organization and or country to another depending on its components (Adegho, 2018).

Okpanel(2017) argued that in a hotel environment, organizational culture can be seen as those ideologies, moralities, attitudes, ethical standards, common values, expectations, shared beliefs, orientations, and specified positions of the firm that brings the component units of an organization together and are shared by its employees for the organizational interest while accommodating

Organizational Culture and Hotel-Quality Services Delivery in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu; Nigeria

the rights and privileges of the employees. A person or group can achieve little or nothing in an organization unless and until such a person becomes familiar with the culture of such place or organization (Keshiro 2015).

However, in a certain situation, an influx of new employees, especially the senior managers, can redefine, modify, rearrange the existing culture of an organization to meet up with his/her new ideologies and visions to the organization. In practice, it is noteworthy that while a firm may have a general culture clearly defining how when things should be done and what should be acceptable by the firm at any given time, secondary cultures do emerge based on feedback mechanisms from customers and work roles or other contingencies (Judith 2011). Interestingly, culture is seen to be durable, practicable, and profitable if experienced, accepted, and interpreted instinctively by individuals in line with their beliefs, and perceive the organization as an integral part of the whole unit to which they (employees) are part of (Okpanel 2013).

Kelvin (2016) noted that culture can be imported, adopted, and learned over a period. In every organization, culture can be learned in two broad ways, which include the trauma model. Here, employees of an organization learn to adjust, cope and adapt to the prevailing situation and threat by building walls of defense and mechanisms around the culture. Secondly, the actual reinforcement model. In this case, things that ordinarily should be open like the employees' benefit, health, security seems to be rooted and encroached.

This study adopted the definition of Okpanel(2017) for organizational culture as a working tool. He defined organizational culture as those ideologies, moralities, attitudes, ethical standards, common values, expectations, shared beliefs, orientations, and specified positions of the firm that brings the component units of an organization together and are shared by its employees for the organizational interest while accommodating the rights and privileges of the employees. This is because the definition captures all the elements needed for smooth and successful service delivery in a hotel business especially in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria.

Total Quality Management and Quality Service Delivery

Recently, the service sector has become an active element in many economies including the economy of Nigeria and total quality management is key to improving quality service delivery especially in the hotel industry (Rich, 2015).

TQM in contemporary management involves a detailed organizational commitment and continuous improvement in all the units in the organization with the vigorous involvement of all members at all levels to ensure quality service thereby meeting or exceeding customer's expectations and gaining their loyalty and making a profit at the end. Ciama (2012) also defines Quality Management as the point in business where all the activities in the system are designed and executed professionally in a manner that customers are satisfied while reducing internal rancor and at a reduced cost and high output. Ndiokho (2012) argued that TQM has helped hotel managers to gain international recognition as customers who patronize. In recognition of the fact that customer needs, yearnings, and wants normally shape and determines in products to be offered in the market by hotel managers, managers of such hotels must pay key attention to the environmental changes such as social, political, economic, and technological to compete effectively and efficiently in the ever tensed hotel business environment.

Service Quality Delivery

Hotel business especially in Enugu State Nigeria is gradually playing a critical and crucial role in the county's economic growth and sustainability. These they do through playing an active role in value creation, which to large extent influences the decision of the managers as well as the purchasing patterns of the customers to the benefit of the organization. For the hospitality industry especially the hotel sector in Enugu to maintain dominance and improve in quality, finance and overall performance, the quality of their service as well as the ethics of the business must be strictly adhered to. Service quality, therefore, has drawn the attention of service providers especially in the hotel industry due to the enormous impact it is making on the customers' satisfaction and the overall effect on the industry's performance.

Linus(2020) noted that customers that patronize hotels prefer and will always value companies that offer high and quality services when compared with their perception, experience, and expectations of what service quality should be. In other words, good service quality, especially in the hospitality industry (hotels), is a key issue in maintaining and surviving in the already intensely competitive business environment like hotels in Enugu Metropolis especially when customers' satisfaction and loyalty is the aim. In Nigeria, tourism is fast-growing and contributing its quota to the economic growth and development; and customers are more concerned about better services quality now than ever. As a result, the link between service actions in the hotel business and service quality is verifiable.

Goyit(2015) noted that the tremendous and dramatic push by hotel operators and firms on quality issues globally now has resulted in stiff competition and good philosophy which emerged as a key determining factor in the choice, patronage, consumption, and loyalty by customers in hotel products and services. Consequently, placement and increased emphasis on good service quality by operators of hotel companies becomes ethical and centers on customer satisfaction.

In the contemporary hospitality industry especially the hotel business, quality service delivery is no doubt a very important component that must be maintained at all times if the hotel must retain or increased its market shares. It involves constant inspection and review of procedures, measures, methods, actions, and products to ensure that services and products delivered are in line with strategic quality standards set at the top management level. Ezinne(2019) opined that hotel firms are today expected not only to

Organizational Culture and Hotel-Quality Services Delivery in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu; Nigeria

offer to their valued customers who are the reason they are in business with qualitative services but also to do any other thing legally possible to retain them in order to put her ahead of other competing firms in the same industry. Hotels that want to take a lead; make a positive impact, and break even in the hospitality industry must consider quality service delivery as a core value in their organizational ethics, culture, and values.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

To buttress the effect of organizational culture, the study pinned on Quality Improvement Theory (QIT) by Deming (1986). This theory focuses on the effort to improve the quality, level, and degree to which management increases the possibility of the desired services and consistently maintain current professional ethics and standard in the industry. Deming (1986) noted that no quality and viable services can be achieved in a service industry without a proper administrative framework embedded in organizational culture, ethics, and values. Here, the administration is expected to put human and material resources into the proper procedures, adopt corporate culture for the organization, and connect the firm to the outside world digitally.

In addition, the theory provides the firm with the means to take out low-quality measures through proactive administrative system control. Management behavior and comportment shape the corporate attitude and exemplify what is vital in achieving a sustainable firm. It also creates a hierarchical context that encourages participation of all within the corporate system by figuring out the best world practices in the service industry to edge out strong competitors in the same field and acquire more market shares. To achieve this, managers need to persistently and positively change the service procedures, measures, items, and patterns thereby imparting on workers' self-actualization and customers satisfaction.

In this study, the QIT bears credence to the fact that organizational culture incorporates total quality management into its managerial practices noting that no quality services or administrative framework could succeed without proper inputs from the top administration. The management puts both human and material resources into suitable ways for the overall benefit of the firm, makes corporate changes as at when due, chooses the best way to serve to attract the best customers, and grows the business to an enviable position. The Theory believes that total quality management (TQM) practices such as QI, quality control, and quality assurance should be incorporated and embedded into the cultural component of an organization if a meaningful impact is to be achieved.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Kemunto (2016) investigated employees' cultural diversity and organizational performance in Nairobi Kenya. The study used a descriptive quantitative research method. Data were collected with a questionnaire administered to respondents of Libya oil gasoline stations Nairobi. Regression analysis was used to find the connection between the variables. It was revealed that employees' belief affects organization performance. The study also found that cultural values affect organization performance in no small means, while employee language has an inverse relationship with organizational performance.

The study of Kemunto (2016) did not state the population of the study neither did it state the sample size from where the analysis was conducted. The study therefore cannot be relied upon.

Taghian (2012) carried out a study on the impact of value similarity on employee commitment in many manufacturing companies in western countries. The survey research design was adopted and a questionnaire was administered to 698 selected respondents from Industries in western countries. The data were analyzed using the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). It was revealed that there is a strong connection between value similarity and employees' commitment, Value Similarity and employees' engagement, external prestige, and mission accomplishment. The study, therefore, resolved that corporate reputation expressively contributes to the branding strategy of the industries. The study recommended that values incorporation in all stages from production to distribution is necessary for an effective and efficient competitive lead.

The study of Taghian (2012) equally failed short of research standard as 'many manufacturing companies in western countries' as used in the study to represent the population and origin are vague. In addition, the conclusion and recommendation of the study deviated from the aim and objective therein.

Yonela and Nita (2018) studied the impact of organizational culture and quality service delivery in the hospitality industry. The study was survey-based research. Data for the study was collected through a self-administered questionnaire to the sampled ninety-six (96) respondents while sixty-one (61) returned their completed questionnaire and was used as sample size. Analysis in the study was through correlation and regression to determine the relationship that exists between the variables. The result revealed that organizational culture has a solid impact on the level of quality service in any hotel.

The study of Yonela and Nita (2018) could not differentiate clearly between the hospitality industry and a hotel firm as the study's aim was on hospitality, its findings were on the hotel.

Finally, as the empirical studies above were reviewed, none of the reviewed studies was carried out on organizational ethics and or culture, linking it to cultural services and heritage, employees' value system. Above all, there was no connection between organizational culture and quality service delivery in hotels in especially in Enugu metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria.

Organizational Culture and Hotel-Quality Services Delivery in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu; Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive survey research design because it described the characteristics of the population in question. 10 registered hotels in Enugu Metropolis with a total staff strength of sixty-nine (69) who have paid their company tax in full as of December 2020 were used as the population and sample size of the study respectively due to the small nature of the population. The questionnaire was designed in a five-point Likert scale format. Validity was tested using face and content technique while Cronbach Alpha statistics was used to establish the reliability of 0.848 using ten pilot respondents. Sixty-two (62) copies of the distributed questionnaire were returned and used for the analysis. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the formulated hypotheses with the aid of SPSS version 23.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.948	.948	10

The table above shows Cronbach's alpha value of 0.848, proving that the tool is highly reliable.

Decision Rule;

Accept the Alternate hypothesis (H_a) if P -value is less than 0.05 (P -value < 0.05); otherwise accept the Null hypothesis (H_0).

Organizational Conduct and Quality Services Delivery.

S/N	Questionnaire Items	SA	A	D	SD	U	Mean	Remark
Organizational Conduct								
1	Organizational conduct affects quality of services delivered in this hotel.	39	23	0	0	0	4.63	Agree
2	Organizational ethics and values affects productivity in hotel business	19	23	15	12	5	4.21	Agree
3	Organizational culture is a collective of traits that make firm what it is	26	28	0	0	8	4.03	Agree
Grand Mean							4.29	Agree

Source: Authors' Computation, 2021

S/N	Quality Service Delivery	SA	A	D	SD	U	Mean	Remark
1	There is no link between quality service and customers loyalty	9	5	27	12	9	2.89	Disagree
2	There is a connect between our firm and our customers through quality services	28	21	3	2	8	3.95	Agree
3	Quality service leads to increased customers retention and sustainability.	23	28	6	0	5	4.03	Agree
Grand Mean							3.62	Agree

Source: Authors' Computation, 2021

Table showing the correlation between organizational behavior and quality service delivery in selected hotels in Enugu Metropolis.

Correlations

		Organizational_behaviour	Quality services
Organizational_behaviour	Pearson Correlation	1	.322**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	62	62
Quality services	Pearson Correlation	.322**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	62	62

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS ver. 23 Outputs.

Organizational Culture and Hotel-Quality Services Delivery in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu; Nigeria

Result Summary

The correlation result above shows that there is a significant association between organizational behavior and quality service delivery in selected hotels in Enugu Metropolis with $r=0.322$, $n=62$, and a p -value of 0.002 ($p<0.5$).

Therefore, the alternate hypothesis is accepted and concludes that there is a significant association between organizational behavior and hotels quality service delivery in Enugu Metropolis. This implies that quality service delivery is influenced greatly by the fundamentals of organizational behavior. This study is in agreement with the findings of Yonela and Nita (2018) who found a positive relationship between organizational culture and quality service delivery.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study investigated the effect of organizational culture on the quality of services offered in hotels in Enugu Metropolis. It was hypothesized that organizational culture has no significant effect on the quality of services delivered in hotels in Enugu Metropolis. On the contrary, the study found a strong and positive relationship between the variables and concludes that organizational culture is pivotal to the quality of services delivered in hotels in Enugu Metropolis. This is to say that when quality is enshrined in the culture of the hotels, there is a high possibility of value increase, customers' satisfaction, patronage, and retention in the organization. The study reasoned that a well-maintained organizational value will influence and contribute positively to service improvement. The integration of good quality services into an organizational value system can not only lead to high customers' patronage but high-profit maximization. The study concluded that organizational culture is vital in achieving quality services to the satisfaction of customers in the hotel industry in Enugu Metropolis.

In the light of the above, the study recommended that management of hotels in Enugu Metropolis should inculcate the organizational value and international best practices to the functionality of her staff as that will help sell out the organizational image to the satisfaction of their customers which is the ultimate in the hotel business.

REFERENCES

- 1) Anyanwu, V.(2013). The effect of company size on the relationship between TQM strategy and organizational performance. *TQM Journal Magazine* 12 (2), 144-148.
- 2) Beauchamp, T. L., Bowie, N. E., & Arnold, D. G. (Eds.). (2018). Ethical theory and business. 7th edition. Pearson Educational International: Upper Saddle River, New Jersey.
- 3) Benjamin, S. N (2011) The balanced scorecard: a new challenge. *Journal of business management*. 34(3), 22-34.
- 4) Bright, E. T. (2013) Development and operations of laboratory proficiency testing guide. *Journal of International Organization for Standardization*. 43(4), 98-104
- 5) Ciama T.Y.(2012). The TQM paradox: relations among TQM practices, plant performance, and customer satisfaction. *Journal of Operations Management*, 17 (1), 59-75.
- 6) Cosmos, A. K (2014) Impact of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance. *International Review of Management and Business Research*. 12(9), 46-56.
- 7) Ibru, G.D.(2018) Beyond Individualism Collectivism: New Cultural Dimensions of value. *Journal of organizational value*, 12(7), 78-83.
- 8) Jabbra, Y.U. & Dwivedi, K.J. (2014) Experiments with New Teaching Models and Methods. *Journal of International Public Management Review*. 5(2): 321-335
- 9) Kings, D.H. & Lui, A.T. (2018) Organizational ethics: A practical approach. Saga Publication: *Journal of management* 334(3), 45-53.
- 10) Lencioni, F.D. (2002) Innovation in Performance Measurement: trends and research implications. *Journal of Management Accounting Research*.32(3), 13-23
- 11) Louis K.O.(2011) Studying organizational culture. *Administrative Science Quarterly*.23(2),29-34.
- 12) Ndiokho, R. (2012). Total quality management programs: A fact or a management fad? *Management Accounting Journal*, 67(5), pp. 36-37.
- 13) Okpanel, K.O. (2017) Analytical Quality Assurance in water Quality monitoring. World Health Organization, Geneva. *Journal of health organization*. 65(6), 321-329.
- 14) Orogbu, L. O & Onyeizugbe, C. (2015) Business and Society: Ethics, Sustainability and stakeholder management. *Journal of management*. 23(4), 12-18.
- 15) Rich, R.(2015). TQM and innovation: A literature review and research framework, Technovation. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 21(9) 539-558.
- 16) Ryan, L.(2013). *Technological innovation strategies*, *Engineering Management Journal* 6(1), 17-24.
- 17) Taghian, E. U. (2012) The influence of value congruence on employee commitment for different industries in western countries. *Journal of employee performance*. 12(3), 565-573.
- 18) Warzecha, G.(2017). Baldrige award may be losing some luster. *The Wall Street Journal*, 11(9), 23-32.

Organizational Culture and Hotel-Quality Services Delivery in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu; Nigeria

- 19) Yonela, G. and Nita, S. (2018). Impact of organizational culture on service quality. Proceedings of the international conference on industrial engineering and operation management. Paris France.